

A holistic framework for production scheduling in Industry 4.0

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Abstract—In today’s highly competitive retail industry, companies must constantly find ways to optimize their processes and improve efficiency in order to stay ahead. This often involves incorporating advanced technology and data-driven approaches to forecasting, inventory management, and production planning to reach the Industry 4.0 standards. In this work, a comprehensive approach is presented that integrates multiple tools and methods to optimize retail processes, including forecasting, safety stock calculation, and batch item production optimization. The proposed pipeline is evaluated using a real-world sales dataset from a dairy company, where a 30-day forecast is generated with low MAPE and sMAPE errors. The performance of the solution is assessed using two safety stock formulas, integrated into the forecast, and optimized using the Wagner-Whitin algorithm. The results showed a significant cost reduction, representing 38.7% of the total cost, compared to a benchmark approach. In conclusion, the proposed methodology is an effective and practical solution for retail companies seeking to improve their operations and gain a competitive advantage.

Index Terms—Industry 4.0, forecasting, scheduling, Wagner-Whitin, safety stock, deep learning

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rise of the digital age, which features an abundance of data sources, intelligent applications and decentralized information storage, companies across all industries face a significant challenge to update their traditional operations and integrate new procedures and tools. This fact is crucial in the manufacturing industry, where the shift towards Industry 4.0 standards has become necessary for survival. Industry 4.0 refers to the integration of various technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and big data analytics to create a highly automated, interconnected and efficient production environment. The adoption of such methodologies has many benefits, including increased efficiency, faster processes, and reduced costs in most sectors. Companies that can successfully implement Industry 4.0 standards to reap the benefits of improved productivity, reduced

errors, and better customer experiences, leading to increased profits and market share. However, despite these significant advantages, many companies struggle with the adoption of new technologies due to the challenges of integrating different operations and ensuring that different functionalities are interoperable. Moreover, there are concerns over data security and privacy, and the need to train employees in new skills. Nonetheless, companies that can overcome these challenges stand to gain a significant competitive advantage in the marketplace. By leveraging technology, they can automate and optimize their production processes, reduce waste, and improve the quality of their products, all of which can translate into increased customer satisfaction and loyalty. In addition, the adoption of Industry 4.0 can open up new revenue streams and business models, such as product-as-a-service and mass customization. Essentially, while the adoption of Industry 4.0 is not without its challenges, it is a vital step for companies that seek to remain competitive in today’s fast-paced and highly digitized business environment. The benefits are clear, and companies that can harness the power of this technological revolution stand to gain a significant advantage over their competitors. [1]–[4].

In this work, a holistic framework regarding three main retail operations is proposed that focuses on interoperability and optimization as part of a general solution that is provided by the KNOWLEDGE project [5]. More specifically:

- A forecasting solution, based on two algorithms for different cases, is proposed.
- Several parametric safety stock formulas that satisfy variability in demand and lead time can be applied to the forecast.
- The optimized production schedule organized in batches for an item is produced using the Wagner-Whitin dynamic programming algorithm.
- Tests are conducted using real data from a retail dairy

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company to validate the approach.

Regarding the existing literature, some of the most known methods for the matter are discussed below.

In [6], the authors propose a modified Wagner-Whitin algorithm accompanied by a custom safety stock formula, based on several factors such as the item's cost, its importance and the expected forecasting error. Additionally, a real case study is employed to show the benefits of the pipeline in saving resources. The key differences with the method introduced in this study, are the type of modification applied to the Wagner-Whitin algorithm, the adaption of a wide variety of metrics that cover a vast range of cases and the adoption of two case specific forecasting methodologies. The findings of this work were applied in Racial Recorders Ltd.

In [7], the authors employing Reinforcement Learning (RL) to optimize both the safety stock and ordering level quantities. This way, a more detailed representation of the features space is used and a more realistic approximation is achieved, contrary to the classical mathematical optimization algorithms that simplify the problem definition in order to find an optimum. They test three RL approaches, a Temporal Difference Advantage Actor-Critic, a Multi-agent Temporal Difference Advantage Actor-Critic and Q-Learning. Their task was to a dual optimization task of minimizing the stock-out levels and the total inventory cost. Their algorithms were comprised from two networks, namely an actor and a critic, the first was responsible for regulating the quantities of each order and the second the safety stock quantities. The results indicate that all three methods perform satisfyingly, however the AC2 approaches are able to reach convergence faster. Additionally, the multi-agent A2C requires fewer data but Q-learning due to its simplicity is quite faster than the two others. Finally, there are some downsides regarding this approach, foremost the overall training and convergence time and the lack of interpretable results that impacts the validity of the models.

In [8], the authors propose two improved Wagner-Whitin variants. Wagner-Whitin is a dynamic programming algorithm that solves lot-sizing models. Practically, it finds an optimal ordering policy in terms of cost. For their first variant, an assumption is made that there is no fluctuation in set-up costs, inventory holding and backlogging. They propose a way to simplify the calculations, meaning that some of them are avoided. For the evaluation, they utilize random data and run simulation with the proposed method and the original one. The results show that there is a significant reduction in run-time. Furthermore, they extend their method, by letting the inventory and set up cost to fluctuate. Again, the speedup is significant, reaching a minimum of 50% in the worst case.

In [9] the author introduces the safety stock problem. More precisely, the selection of the correct inventory level to minimize both stock outs, and subsequently lost sales, and inventory cost. A presentation of several methods and formulas with several variables is taking place, with each one of them being appropriate for specific cases. Finally, it mentioned that each item should be handled individually, to determine the point that each order is placed.

A dynamic programming method to solve the economic lot size model is presented in [10] and [11]. The authors assume that the demand for a specific item is pre-determined for a time period T , along with the holding and setup costs to be able to fluctuate throughout this time-span. The aim is to achieve a minimum cost related to the inventory scheduling.

A comparative analysis, of methods related to the lot-sizing problem with manufacturing, is examined in [12]. An updated Wagner-Whitin method is introduced accompanied by a dynamic methodology to determine the size of a partial version of the algorithm's formulation, making use of a cost-based structure. The proposed method performs better than the literature and achieves a rate of 96% in optimally solved problems. The later test were conducted with various parameters, making the algorithm quite robust.

In [13], a combination of Activity-based costing (ABC) method in order to determine the significance of raw materials and two lot-sizing optimization algorithms, namely Wagner-Whitin and Silver-Meal, are examined. They use a case study with several raw materials to evaluate their hypothesis. Firstly, the ABC method is used and detects a product of A class, which is the only one that belongs to the class. Then, the ordering policy of this item is optimized using the methods mentioned above. The results show that using this strategy, a cost cut of 1.81% can be achieved. The two algorithms perform quite similar, with Wagner-Whitin performing slightly better in terms of total cost reduction.

In [14], again, tackles the Lot-Sizing problem without adding a constrained in capacity. The proposed algorithm is a linear complexity algorithm operating data structures that have not employed before, and is based on the Wagner-Whitin cost method. After several experiments, the proposed method is evidently being simpler and faster compared with other similar linear approaches.

Another variation of the original Wagner-Whitin algorithm is introduced in [15]. The authors propose a Robust approach to deal with cost uncertainty when it is non-stationary and correlated, without any other related information other than the mean and covariance of the variables. In order to evaluate the methodology, they compared it with the original Wagner Within but with known costs. The results showed that the difference between them is quite small in terms of cost. Their solution is tailored for one product. Also, they state that a comparison with related methods described in the literature, would be not valid due to the assumption they make regarding the distribution of the costs.

In [16], the authors propose a supply chain management RL approach that adapts and optimizes the whole process. This methodology consists of a Markov Process that is optimized by a learning algorithm. The whole process simulates the environment and deduces the results of certain changes in parameters. Overall, this approach provides the user with flexibility for several cases, where other simpler algorithms fail due to uncertainty. To evaluate the model, a case study of several production stages was created. The results showed that the algorithm outperforms its counterpart. Finally, the authors

state that in cases with even more complex problems and data, the procedure will be much more effective.

The authors in [17] introduce a real-world example of a solution for production scheduling optimization and production line balancing based on genetic algorithm in order to boost factories of the future to be self-learned and capable to act in monetary situations. This work presents the optimization solution, the way the proposed cognitive platform can be modified for serving other use cases besides the anomaly detection, in order to provide a complete tool for factory automation and optimization.

In summary, the Wagner-Whitin algorithm and its variants have proven to be valuable tools for addressing the challenges of inventory management. These algorithms have been widely used and studied, and have been shown to be effective in minimizing holding and production costs while still satisfying demand. In addition, incorporating different formulas for safety stock into the Wagner-Whitin algorithm can provide a more accurate representation of inventory management in real-world scenarios and lead to more effective decision-making. However, it appears to be a gap, in the research regarding the combination of multiple safety stock formulas into the Wagner-Whitin, accompanied by a complete forecasting solution.

The motivation of this work is to provide a holistic approach for SME's, offering a full-stage solution: forecasting of future product demands utilizing Light Gradient Boosting Model machine learning algorithm or a framework of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) with a boosting stage, calculation of safety stock for each product taking into account the demand patterns and finally the optimization of company's production planning utilizing Wagner-Whitin algorithm. This framework is applied on sales data from a dairy company.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II the proposed methodology is presented and more specifically the Wagner-Whitin algorithm, the safety stock policy and the forecasting procedures. In Section III, a brief description of the dataset used is provided, while in Section IV, the experimental results of the proposed approach are presented. Finally, in Section V we draw our conclusions.

II. PROPOSED APPROACH

In this section, a brief description of the scientific-based approach of Wagner-Whitin algorithm along with the safety stock policy are provided. The main parts of the proposed methodology are presented next.

A. Wagner-Within algorithm

Wagner-Within developed an algorithm to find the optimal lot size for each period when net requirements are known for several periods into the future. Generally, the algorithm minimizes the cost of ordering by optimally combining the net requirements for one or more periods and evaluates all possible ways of ordering to cover demand in each period of the planning horizon.

TABLE I
SERVICE LEVEL WITH THE CORRESPONDING Z SCORE

Service Level	Z score
85%	1.0
90%	1.3
95%	1.6
99%	2.3

The standard equations proposed by Wagner and Within, to calculate the price of the minimum cost program for periods 1 to k , when the inventory at period k is zero are:

$$f_k = \min_{0 \leq j < k} [f_j + m_{jk}] \quad (1)$$

$$m_{jk} = a_{j+1} + c_{j+1}b_{j+1} + \sum_{t=j+1}^{k-1} h_t \sum_{r=t+1}^k d_r \quad (2)$$

where f_k is the minimum cost program for period 1 to period k when the inventory level at period k is zero. m_{jk} is the cost incurred in periods $j+1$ through k , a_{j+1} is the fixed cost if an order is made in period $j+1$, c_{j+1} is the cost of producing each unit in period $j+1$, b_{j+1} is the number of units produced/bought in period $j+1$, h_t is the cost of keeping a produced unit in the warehouse from period t to period $t+1$ and d_r is the estimated demand for period r [10].

B. Safety stock policy

Stock inventory usually consists of cycle stocks, the inventory that is expected to be sold within a given period, and safety stock. Safety stock acts as a buffer amount that accounts for uncertainties such as, excess demand, supplier delays, inaccurate inventory forecasts, inaccurate demand, failure to place timely reorders and financial constraints. Safety stock mitigates the risks and consequences of stock outs, allowing the production company supply chain to proceed as usual even after cycle stock runs out. In this work, the Safety Stock may appear with the abbreviation Ss , for simplicity.

There are several formulas in the scientific literature regarding the calculation of the safety stock, that have different parameters and are suited for different cases. The simplest is with the use of the historical average demand multiplied by the days that are desired to have emergency stock for.

$$Ss = \text{days of stock} * AVG(h \text{ demand}) \quad (3)$$

Another formula uses the *service level factor*. The service level is considered as the probability of remaining out of stock. For example, when the service level is 85%, the company is secured for this amount of cases, but there is a 15% chance of stock out. In order to calculate the stock amount, this probability is translated to a factor Z .

In addition, there is also the use of *lead time*, which is the total time period needed for production and distribution of the product. The distribution that is assumed the data are following is Gaussian. The final formula has as follows:

$$S_s = Z * \sqrt{LT/T} * \sigma_D \quad (4)$$

where LT is the total lead time and L is the time periods used for calculating the standard deviation of demand. In essence, this fraction equals the average lead time. This equation can be also found with the name of Haizer-Render.

For cases, that the lead time is the most volatile feature, the average of the demand is used multiplied by the standard deviation of lead time. The final form of the formula is:

$$S_s = Z * D_{avg} * \sigma_{LT} \quad (5)$$

This method is also known as Greasley's.

Finally, another formula that is optimal for lead times that are brief is the average-max. In order to use it, the maximum and the average levels of sales should be calculated. In addition, the max and the average lead time are also used.

$$S_s = (max_{sales} * max_{LT}) - (avg_{sales} * avg_{LT}) \quad (6)$$

C. Methodology description

Overall, the proposed methodology is comprised from three separate parts. The first part is the demand forecast, the second is the incorporation of safety stock into the forecast and the third the calculation of the production schedule. The input of the method is the historical sales of a single or several product codes, while the outputs is the forecast of demand for a time period of 30 days accompanied by the optimized batch production schedule for the product.

The method discussed in the paper starts by acquiring sales data along with information about the product families. This data is then used to generate features through an aggregation process that combines the temporal information with product information. The purpose of this process is to identify patterns and relationships between the sales data and the product families, which can be used to create more accurate forecasts for items that lack sufficient historical data.

After the feature generation stage, the prediction stage begins. This stage involves using machine learning algorithms to forecast future demand for the products. In this case, the authors have chosen to use a Light Gradient Boosting Model (LGBM), a tree-based algorithm that utilizes boosting to improve its predictions or an ensemble of shallow Recurrent neural networks accompanied by a boosting stage conducted by a shallow feed-forward neural network (NN). The selection between the two methods is based on the available additional data regarding the products, their history, and the complexity of the demand-sales time series.

The next stage of the process is the safety stock calculation, which plays a crucial role in inventory management. The goal of the safety stock calculation is to compensate for any potential forecasting error and provide the company with an additional buffer of inventory to avoid lost sales. This helps to ensure that the company has the necessary stock on hand to meet customer demand, even when there are unexpected fluctuations in demand.

To calculate the safety stock, the forecasted quantities from the previous stage are required. Different formulas and strategies can be used to calculate the safety stock, and a per-item approach is often preferred. This means that the safety stock is calculated separately for each product, taking into consideration the specific characteristics and demand patterns of each one.

In addition to selecting the most appropriate formula, the management must also consider the production cycle of each product. This parameter is used to account for restrictions that may impact the availability of stock, such as short expiration dates or production line unavailability. By taking into account the production cycle and selecting the most suitable formula, the safety stock calculation provides an updated forecast with the addition of the safety stock quantities for the selected products. This helps to ensure that the company has a flexible and reliable inventory management system in place.

The final part of the methodology proposed focuses on the optimization of the quantities produced. This is accomplished using the Wagner-Whitin algorithm, which is a commonly used dynamic programming approach for the lot-sizing problem. The algorithm takes as inputs the updated forecast, as well as the set-up cost of production and the daily upkeep cost of each product. Additionally, the proposed variant allows for further parametrization by using the initial or final quantities of the product as input.

The algorithm evaluates all potential costs for each day and then conducts a backward crawl to determine the combination of produced quantities and production timeline that minimizes the total cost. This is done by considering the set-up cost of production and the daily upkeep cost of each product, as well as any initial or final quantities of the product that may be available.

In conclusion, after the final stage, the user is presented with a 30-day forecast for all available items, with safety stock added for the selected products that the management has chosen. Additionally, the optimized production schedule is designed to minimize cost for the selected quantities and provides a detailed timeline for the production process. The combination of the updated forecast, safety stock, and optimized production schedule results in a comprehensive and holistic solution for the inventory management problem that considers both cost minimization and customer demand. In Figure 1 below, the whole process and its specific stages are illustrated.

III. DATASET DESCRIPTION

The proposed methodology for forecasting sales was tested and evaluated using real-life sales data from the dairy company PARMALAT S.P.A, Collecchio, Italy. The data contain sales information for different products and information about the characteristics of each item, such as product family, packaging etc.

The sales data consisted of 175 distinct items that were monitored for a period of 10 months. However, the sales history of some items was limited, with some having sales data

Fig. 1. Overview of the steps of the proposed methodology.

for only one day, while others had sales data for 273 days. This disparity in sales history made the task of forecasting more challenging, and as a result, a threshold was set to determine which products would be included in the forecasting process. The sales data and product information were used to extract relationships between similar products and provide valuable insights into the sales patterns of the different items.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This case study aims to demonstrate the entire pipeline of the proposed method by focusing on a single item from the dataset. To start, the selected item was isolated from the forecasted data and the safety stock was calculated using two of the proposed formulas. These formulas considered both historical data and predicted demand, and included various parameters, such as lead time and service rate. The calculated safety stock was then added to the predictions and used as input in the Wagner-Whitin algorithm, which optimally scheduled the production process. Finally, the proposed method was

compared to a naive benchmark of “day before production” to evaluate the cost difference and highlight the benefits of the pipeline. This case study demonstrated the effectiveness of incorporating safety stock into the production process, leading to a more efficient and cost-effective operation.

A. Forecasting

As mentioned before, the dataset was comprised by two tabular sub datasets. These data were merged together and an extensive feature engineering process followed, resulting in 94 features. Then the LGBM algorithm produced a forecast for 30 days for each individual item (see Figure 4 the production forecast for a specified product). The symmetric Mean Absolute Percentage error (sMAPE) of the forecast reaches 33% while MAPE is 40% which are quite satisfactory metrics considering the limited historical data included in the particular dataset.

Fig. 2. Sales forecast with the LGBM.

However, in case where no additional data regarding the product families are provided and the historical data for the products are not extended, as in our case, another solution is proposed. This consists of an Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD), in order to simplify the sales time series and create additional features, and a framework of eight shallow RNNs using Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) that are trained on the features produced from the decomposition. Each network is tasked with predicting the next 30 values of the simplified time series. The next stage includes the application of a boosting NN on the predictions in order to add them and correct them. This solution is based only on auto regression due to the absence of additional data. Finally, it is worth noting that the forecast is for a single item each time.

The architecture of the proposed framework based on RNNs is illustrated in Figure 3. Where the EMD has generated eight time series and these are used as input in eight different RNNs.

The sMAPE for the selected item using the Ensemble method is 19.6% and the MAPE 27.7%, again, these results are considered quite good due to the limited sales data and the high amount of volatility they had.

Fig. 3. The architecture of the RNN framework.

Fig. 4. Sales forecast with the RNN framework.

For showcasing of the entire pipeline, the forecast of an item produced by the LGBM algorithm was selected.

B. Safety Stock

In this case study, the basic stock formula and the Heizer-Render formula were utilized to calculate the safety stock. This was because the lead time was constant with no deviations or fluctuations. As a result, the Average Max and Greasley's Formulas, which are based on changes in lead time, were not appropriate in this scenario. The calculated safety stock was then incorporated into the forecast data as part of the production process. It is important to note that the choice of safety stock formula should always be informed by the specific requirements of the production process, including the lead time, the variability of demand, and the desired level of inventory.

In the Heizer-Render example, the service rate was set to 85%, indicating that there is a low probability of stock shortage in the production cycle. The lead time of 7 days

was determined to be constant, based on recommendations from the dairy company providing the data. This lead time has a significant impact on the calculation of safety stock, as it represents the time between ordering an item and receiving it. The production cycle of 7 days, the frequency of the safety stock calculation, was also determined to be constant. The additional 456 items of safety stock added to the forecasted quantities are crucial to ensuring that the production process runs smoothly and that there is minimal disruption due to stock shortages. Figure 5 demonstrates the added safety stock in relation to the actual forecast, highlighting the importance of incorporating safety stock into the production planning process.

Fig. 5. The added Heizer-Render safety stock for the selected product.

In the second example, the basic safety stock formula was employed. This method considers the historical data of the product and calculates its mean value. The user selects the number of days they want stock for and in this case, a one-day stock with a restocking cycle of 7 days was chosen. This resulted in a total of 669 added items of safety stock. Figure 6, depicts the allocation of this safety stock.

Fig. 6. The added basic safety stock for the selected product.

When comparing the two formulas with the chosen parameters, it is important to note that the basic formula heavily relies on historical values, which can result in the addition of more items. However, this dependence on past values may not be ideal when considering future forecasts. In contrast, the Heizer-Render formula takes into account the future forecasted values and can be more advantageous if the forecast is accurate. However, if there is a significant error in the forecast, the basic formula may be a better option. It is important to consider the trade-off between the two formulas when determining the calculation of safety stock. The choice of formula will depend on the accuracy of the forecast, the desired level of inventory, and the potential impact of stock outs or overstock.

C. Production Scheduling Optimization

The last section of the pipeline is the optimization of the production batch allocation. This is accomplished by the modified Wagner-Whitin. The parameters were the same for both experiments. A holding cost of 1\$ was set for each item's upkeep cost and a setup cost of 500\$ for each day that the production takes place. Furthermore, the initial and final quantity were set to zero, but as explained before due to the modifications, the algorithm can have non-zero values for these parameters.

Fig. 7. The scheduled production quantities using the basic stock formula.

Figure 7 shows the production plan for 30 days ahead of a specified product, where the production quantities are depicted with the gray bars, while the demand with black. It is evident, that production is not scheduled for every day. For the case, of using the basic formula, 11 days out of 30 include a production operation. The quantities, costs, and days are shown in detail in Table II.

The total cost, based on the optimized production, reaches 9194\$, with the quantities being relatively distributed in a uniform manner. For the other formula the batches were allocated quite similarly, the only differences are in day 1, 8, 15, 22 and 29 where there are slight deviation (see Table III). The total cost is the same as in the other example. That

TABLE II
PRODUCTION INFORMATION FOR BASIC SAFETY STOCK.

Production day	Quantity	Cumulative Cost
1	586	1063
5	539	2097
8	638	3257
12	528	4265
15	570	5175
18	337	5835
20	304	6471
22	464	7259
25	362	7943
27	292	8573
29	429	9194

TABLE III
PRODUCTION INFORMATION FOR HEIZER-RENDER SAFETY STOCK.

Production day	Quantity	Cumulative Cost
1	574	1063
5	539	2097
8	597	3257
12	528	4265
15	487	5175
18	337	5835
20	304	6471
22	448	7259
25	362	7943
27	292	8573
29	368	9194

is, because the setup cost is constant and independent to the produced quantities.

In order to evaluate the optimization process and the whole pipeline, the results of the proposed method, were compared with a benchmark approach regarding the production scheduling. This approach was the “day-before-production”. Practically, this means the for each day, the forecasted quantity will be produced the previous day. The cost of this method is constant and equal to the setup cost times the days of production, without the addition of holding costs.

As the results, demonstrate the cost catted by the method is over 5000\$ for both cases. More specifically, there is a difference of 5806\$ between the benchmark and the proposed methods, this can translate into 38.7% reduction in cost. However, there are cases where the product schedule is similar to the Benchmark approach. Practically, this means that the optimization process procures the solution of “day-before-production”. Although, this is something the Wagner-Whiting will determine, and there is no doubt that the solution with the minimum cost will be selected.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In order for a retail company to remain competitive, various factors must be taken into consideration, including the optimization of their retail processes. This study presents a comprehensive approach that incorporates forecasting based on machine learning algorithms, calculation of safety stock, and batch item production scheduling optimization. The proposed pipeline consists of two forecasting methods, each

designed for a specific case, four safety stock formulas that consider demand variability, lead time variability, or both, and a variation of the Wagner-Whitin dynamic programming algorithm to schedule an optimized production plan for each selected item. To evaluate the performance of the solution, a dataset of a dairy company's sales is used, where a 30-day forecast is generated with low MAPE and sMAPE errors, taking into account the unique characteristics of the data. Two of the safety stock formulas are applied and the additional quantities are integrated into the forecast. Finally, the optimization using the Wagner-Whitin method results in a cost reduction of over 5800 dollars, representing 38.7% of the total cost, compared to a benchmark approach. In conclusion, the proposed methodology is a complete and effective pipeline for institutions seeking to optimize their internal processes.

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REFERENCES

- [1] W. de Paula Ferreira, F. Armellini, and L. A. De Santa-Eulalia, "Simulation in industry 4.0: A state-of-the-art review," *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, vol. 149, p. 106868, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.cie.2020.106868.
- [2] A. G. Frank, L. S. Dalenogare, and N. F. Ayala, "Industry 4.0 technologies: Implementation patterns in manufacturing companies," *International Journal of Production Economics*, vol. 210, pp. 15–26, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.ijpe.2019.01.004.
- [3] I. Antoniuk, R. Svitek, M. Krajčovič, and B. Furmannová, "Methodology of design and optimization of internal logistics in the concept of Industry 4.0," *Transportation Research Procedia*, vol. 55, pp. 503–509, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.trpro.2021.07.093.
- [4] R. Csalódi, Z. Süle, S. Jaskó, T. Holczinger, and J. Abonyi, "Industry 4.0-Driven Development of Optimization Algorithms: A Systematic Overview," *Complexity*, vol. 2021, p. e6621235, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1155/2021/6621235.
- [5] S. Alvarez-Napagao et al., "knowlEdge Project –Concept, Methodology and Innovations for Artificial Intelligence in Industry 4.0," in *2021 IEEE 19th International Conference on Industrial Informatics (INDIN)*, Jul. 2021, pp. 1–7. doi: 10.1109/INDIN45523.2021.9557410.
- [6] J. Potamianos, A. J. Orman, and A. K. Shahani, "Modelling for a dynamic inventory-production control system," *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 96, no. 3, pp. 645–658, Feb. 1997, doi: 10.1016/0377-2217(95)00256-1.
- [7] E. E. Kosasih and A. Brintrup, "Reinforcement Learning Provides a Flexible Approach for Realistic Supply Chain Safety Stock Optimisation," *arXiv*, Jul. 02, 2021. Accessed: Jan. 16, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2107.00913>.
- [8] SAJADI, SJ, MB GH ARIANEZHAD, and Habitat Alah Sadeghi. "An Improved WAGNER-WHITIN Algorithm." (2009): 117-123.
- [9] A. Constantin, "INVENTORY MANAGEMENT, SERVICE LEVEL AND SAFETY," no. 9.
- [10] H. Wagner and T. Whitin, "Dynamic version of the economic lot-size model," *Management Science*, vol. 5(1), pp. 89–96, 1958.
- [11] H. M. Wagner and T. M. Whitin, "Dynamic Version of the Economic Lot Size Model," *Management Science*, vol. 50, no. 12, pp. 1770–1774, 2004.
- [12] J. O. Cunha and R. A. Melo, "A computational comparison of formulations for the economic lot-sizing with remanufacturing," *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, vol. 92, pp. 72–81, Feb. 2016, doi:10.1016/j.cie.2015.11.024.
- [13] D. Ernawati, S. Dewi, N. K. Sari, and K. Budianto, "Ordering Size Optimization of Raw Material to Minimize Inventory Costs using Wagner-Whitin Algorithm and Silver-Meal Methods," *E3S Web Conf.*, vol. 328, p. 05002, 2021, doi: 10.1051/e3sconf/202132805002.
- [14] N. T. Chowdhury, M. F. Baki, and A. Azab, "Dynamic Economic Lot-Sizing Problem: A new O(T) Algorithm for the Wagner-Whitin Model," *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, vol. 117, pp. 6–18, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.cie.2018.01.010.
- [15] P. Hanafizadeh, A. Shahin, and M. Sajadifar, "Robust Wagner-Whitin algorithm with uncertain costs," *J Ind Eng Int*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 435–447, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1007/s40092-018-0298-y.
- [16] I. Giannoccaro and P. Pontrandolfo, "Inventory management in supply chains: a reinforcement learning approach", *International Journal of Production Economics*, vol. 78, no. 2, pp. 153–161, Jul. 2002, doi: 10.1016/S0925-5273(00)00156-0.
- [17] K. Georgiadis, A. Nizamis, T. Vafeiadis, D. Ioannidis and D. Tzovaras, "Production Scheduling Optimization enabled by Digital Cognitive Platform", *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 204, pp. 424-431, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2022.08.052